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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Review Article****REVIEW OF SLEEVE GASTRECTOMY INDICATIONS AND
PROCEDURES**¹Fandi Alanazi, ²Sarah Albassam, ³Alanazi Mohammed**Abstract:**

Global prevalence of excessive weight has risen. Where lifestyle and clinical therapies have actually stopped working, laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) is increasingly considered as an excellent surgery for morbid obesity. We conducted search using electronic biomedical databases such as; Medline, and Embase, for studies published up to 2018 with English language concerning the sleeve gastrectomy indications and procedures. Sleeve gastrectomy, also called a vertical sleeve gastrectomy, is a surgical weight-loss process. This treatment is generally performed laparoscopically, which involves placing tiny tools via numerous tiny incisions in the top abdomen. During sleeve gastrectomy, concerning 80 percent of the stomach is eliminated, leaving a tube-shaped stomach regarding the size and shape of a banana. Restricting the dimension of the stomach limits the amount of food you have the ability to eat. Additionally, the procedure motivates hormonal changes that assist with weight reduction. The same hormone modifications also help relieve problems associated with being overweight, such as hypertension or heart disease. Sleeve gastrectomy can give lasting weight-loss. The amount of weight you shed depends upon the modification in lifestyle behaviors. It is possible to shed approximately 60 percent, or even a lot more, of the excess weight within 2 years.

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INTRODUCTION:

Morbid obesity has become a world-wide health problem [1]. The percentage of overweight adults [Body Mass Index (BMI) of 25 kg/m² or greater] has actually boosted year on year from 1980 to 2013 (28.8 to 36.9 % in males, and from 29.8 to 38.0 % in women) [1]. Recent data from the Ireland has actually recognized a comparable issue, with 22.9 % of males and 22.5 % of women being classified as overweight [1]. This substantial increase in BMI and weight problems has caused many public health strategies promoting calorie reduction and increased physical activity. A lot of these have resulted in excellent schemes such as cycle to work schemes, healthy and balanced lunches in schools, etc. However, despite strenuous efforts the obesity endemic has continued to rise. In straight relationship with weight problems, there has been a significant rise in obesity-related morbidities [Type II Diabetes (T2DM), obstructive sleep apnoea, high blood pressure, cardiovascular diseases and obesity-related cancers cells] [2]. This impact has actually had a substantial effect on health-related expense both straight and indirectly. In 2010, obese and excessive weight were directly associated with 3.4 million deaths, and 4 % of disability-adjusted life-years globally [2].

Diet plan, exercise, and behavior modification, typically referred to as conservative therapy, can lead to short-term fat burning (approximately 10 % body weight), however this is typically not sustained, with the majority reclaiming weight with time. Conversely, bariatric surgery is acknowledged as the most reliable treatment for patients with a BMI of 40, or a BMI of 35 with relevant co-morbidities. Presently, there are three primary categories of bariatric procedures: malabsorption treatments; restrictive methods and a combination of both [1]. Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) is a restrictive procedure and is approved as being reasonably risk-free with a relatively low rate of difficulty and reoperation [3]. The procedure involves the elimination of the majority of the fundus of the stomach, producing a gastric "tube", which in turn limits the capacity for food intake [3].

Global prevalence of excessive weight has risen. Where lifestyle and clinical therapies have actually stopped working, laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) is increasingly considered as an excellent surgery for morbid obesity

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted search using electronic biomedical databases such as; Medline, and Embase, for studies

published up to 2018 with English language concerning the sleeve gastrectomy indications and procedures, Following MeSh terms were used in our search strategy: "sleeve gastrectomy", "indication", "procedures". more relevant studies were searched in the references list of included studies.

DISCUSSION:

- **Why it's done**

Sleeve gastrectomy is done to aid you lose excess weight and decrease your risk of possibly life-threatening weight-related illness, including:

- Gastroesophageal reflux disease
- Heart disease
- High blood pressure
- High cholesterol
- Obstructive sleep apnea
- Type 2 diabetes
- Stroke
- Infertility

Sleeve gastrectomy is commonly done only after you've attempted to lose weight by boosting your diet regimen and exercise practices.

In general, sleeve gastrectomy surgical treatment could be an option for you if ^[3]:

- Your body mass index (BMI) is 40 or greater (extreme weight problems).
- Your BMI is 35 to 39.9 (excessive weight), and you have a serious weight-related health problem, such as type 2 diabetic issues, high blood pressure or severe sleep apnea. In many cases, you might receive particular types of weight-loss surgical procedure if your BMI is 30 to 34 and you have significant weight-related illness.

Patient should additionally agree to make irreversible adjustments to lead a much healthier way of life, may be called for to take part in long-term follow-up plans that consist of checking your nutrition, your way of life and behavior, and your clinical conditions.

- **Risks**

Similar to any major surgery, sleeve gastrectomy poses prospective health and wellness dangers, both in the short term and long-term.

Risks related to the sleeve gastrectomy can consist of ^[4]:

- Excessive bleeding
- Infection
- Adverse reactions to anesthesia

- Blood clots
- Lung or breathing problems
- Leaks from the cut edge of the stomach

Longer term risks and complications of sleeve gastrectomy surgery can include:

- Gastrointestinal obstruction
- Hernias
- Gastroesophageal reflux
- Low blood sugar (hypoglycemia)
- Malnutrition
- Vomiting

Very rarely, complications of sleeve gastrectomy can be fatal.

- **The technique**

SG is a bariatric technique consisting of subtotal vertical gastrectomy with preservation of the pylorus, including longitudinal resection of fundus, corpus

and antrum, to produce a tubular duct along the minimal curvature. Resection makes up about 80% of the stomach and the remnant gastric has a capacity > 100 mL. It is thought about an easier method than various other procedures such as Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB), since numerous anastomoses are needed [4]. (Figure 1). Variants of SG have actually been defined, and although no relative studies have actually been conducted, none seems to supply advantages. Moreover, SG has actually been executed with various levels of intestinal bypass, including variations with 2 exits from the stomach such as SG transportation with bipartition and SG with loop bipartition [4]. In an effort to attain a surgery with even more metabolic effects, SG has actually likewise been related to ileal transposition; lastly, short-term studies on SG with a gastric band have actually been reported [5].

Figure 1. Sleeve gastrectomy [4].

- **Mechanism**

SG yields far better results than various other restrictive methods and resembles RYGB in regards to weight reduction and carbohydrate metabolic rate renovation in the brief and average term [6]. This SG superiority over various other restrictive techniques has been related to various devices such as alteration of intestinal motility, hormone systems, alterations in

bile acids and gut microbiote.

Unlike other limiting methods such as gastric banding, SG prompts a rapid gastric emptying and sped up digestive transit [7]. It seems that the rapid transit may activate hormone mechanisms that will be described below; it might additionally trigger raised satiation, as occurs with medicines that boost gastric

emptying [7].

GLP-1 is an incretin hormone secreted by L-cells of the distal intestinal tract in response to eating. It has valuable impacts on weight and glucose metabolism given that it advertises insulin secretion, hinders gastric emptying, glucagon secretion and hepatic glucose production [8]. SG has repeatedly generated an overstated postprandial increase in GLP-1 comparable to that of RYGB. In the last, the surge in GLP-1 could be explained by the hind-gut hypothesis, in which stimulation of the distal gut caused by the bypass cause an amplified rise in GLP-1. However, after SG, the system through which the surgery would certainly enhance GLP-1 secretion is uncertain. One hypothesis could be that the improved transit arising from SG likewise causes distal intestine stimulation [6]. An additional opportunity would certainly occur from the absence of gastric feedback to the digestive tract signals that usually slow-moving emptying [6]. Others have actually recommended that an increase in GLP-1 degrees would be an effort to bring back digestive tract gastric motility in feedback to sped up gastric emptying. Because GLP-1 reaction is additionally raised by instilling nutrients directly into the duodenum, the presence of an independent gastric emptying device has actually also been suggested [6]. Moreover, offered the rapid rise in GLP-1 complying with intake and probably before nutrients contact L-cells, the presence of a proximal-distal circuit creating GLP-1 secretion has been suggested that does not need direct get in touch with between chime and L-cells, which could be moderated through a neural or hormone pathway via cholecystokinin (CCK) [7].

Peptide YY (PYY), likewise known as peptide tyrosine or pancreatic peptide YY3-36, is an anorexigenic peptide launched by L-cells in mucosa of the gastrointestinal tract, specifically the ileum and colon, in reaction to feeding. In addition to decrease appetite, PYY boosts nutrition absorption in the ileum, inhibits gastric and pancreatic secretion, undermines gallbladder contraction and reduces gastric emptying. Reduced secretion in obese patients, which is connected with reduced satiation, has actually been reported [9]. Like GLP 1, various studies have actually shown a considerable rise in PYY after SG, and again the results are comparable to those observed after RYGB, recommending that the mechanism for rise will certainly be shared [9]. Ghrelin is a neuropeptide with orexigenic action predominantly synthesized by oxyntic cells of the gastric fundus [10]. Under physiologic problems, ghrelin levels boost during fasting with a preprandial

height and are subdued by food. It also has diabetogenic results such as the suppression of insulin secretion [10]. A drop-in ghrelin concentration after SG contrasted to baseline levels and various other restrictive techniques or RYGB has actually continually been shown. This drop off has actually been connected with fundus resection and there is supposition that it may be just one of the primary mechanisms accounting for the prevalence of SG over various other limiting strategies and its similarity to RYGB. Nevertheless, some experimental research studies located that the decline in ghrelin concentrations might not be crucial. Chambers et al showed that ghrelin-deficient mice remained to slim down, had actually boosted glucose metabolism and inappetence for fatty foods after SG [11]. Nevertheless, the writers advised that a feasible compensatory system in ghrelin-deficient animals might underestimate the impacts of surgical procedure. In favor of the valuable effects of ghrelin reduction after SG, a boost in ghrelin after weight management by diet regimen or by other limiting techniques has actually been observed. This suggests that weight loss triggers compensatory systems to recover weight that could be erased after SG [12].

Leptin, synthesized in white adipose tissue proportionally to the amount of body fat, minimizes intake and body weight via activities in the main nerve system. In weight problems, a reduced sensitivity to leptin has been recommended, causing a failure to find satiety regardless of high energy shops. It is uncertain whether the improvement in leptin resistance plays a straight duty in weight management after SG. While relevant genetics appear to increase its expression, current research studies suggest that the reversal of leptin resistance could be managed by healthy protein accessibility [13].

Raising endocrine functions for bile acids have been acknowledged and associated with a boosted GLP-1 feedback, carbohydrate metabolic process improvement and minimizing liver steatosis [13]. The raised serum bile acid concentrations after SG are possibly associated with rapid transit that will increase their accessibility in the location of maximum absorption, the incurable ileum. It likewise appears that these impacts could be mediated by the farsenoid X receptor (FXR), since Ryan et al showed that this pathway is needed to enhance glucose metabolic rate, protect against countervailing hyperphagia and preserve long-lasting weight loss after SG [14].

Another system which possibly affects the metabolic benefits of SG is the adjustment in the gut microbiome, which enhances the flora composition as

in lean subjects in a similar method to however much less striking than RYGB. Although the devices are yet to be discovered, the way is open to a complex and appealing system of host-bacteria interactions [14].

With a sight of greater perspective, control energy homeostasis involves an advanced interaction system amongst the gut, adipose tissue and central nerve system [15]. Via hormonal and neural signals, the main nerve system incorporates the info on what happens in the gut, e.g., type and quantity of consumed nutrients and on energy reserves and acts by managing hunger, satiety and feeding actions. For instance, against an unfavorable energy balance, this system might compensate by hyperphagia or increasing choice for high-calorie food to bring back regular weight [15]. In this regard, the trick for the performance of SG as metabolic surgical procedure appears to depend on protecting against these offsetting feedbacks, modifying both hormonal and neural signaling paths or perhaps bring about adjustments at central level.

- **Indications and contraindications**

Laparoscopic SG needs to be thought about a primary bariatric treatment or the initial stage of a 2-step method for the management of morbidly overweight patients [16]. In the later on, LSG has been made use of to deal with at first incredibly obese or high-risk patients, before a potential second-stage bariatric procedure (mainly RYGB) is done, within 2 years. It is important that all patients undergo comprehensive interdisciplinary assessment by a group of specialists experienced in obesity management and bariatric surgical procedure. Sleeve gastrectomy candidates must undergo routine preoperative evaluation, like any other significant stomach surgery. Laparoscopic SG follows the signs and standards of all various other bariatric treatments [17]. As a result, it should be provided to morbidly overweight patients with metabolic syndrome and to patients with a BMI of 35 kg/m² and linked co-morbidities [17].

Super obese patients, with BMI > 50 kg/m², can be used LSG as this treatment appears to be likewise effective for this team of patients [18]. Nonetheless, incredibly obese patients often tend to restore weight after the very first 12 months of follow-up, while preserving the renovation in co-morbidities. Taking into consideration the above some authors think that LSG needs to be the first step of a 2-step treatment for the management of incredibly obese patients. Laparoscopic SG appears to be a possible and secure treatment for risky medical patients. It can be used as a risk-free initial operation in order to achieve rapid weight-loss in high-risk patients who require to

undertake a 2nd non-bariatric treatment such as knee replacement, nephrectomy or spinal column surgical treatment [19]. Chaudhry et al and Tariq et al have also published appealing data relating to morbidly obese patients with end-stage organ failing that effectively underwent LSG [20], [21]. Laparoscopic SG has shown to be practically viable and reliable in obese patients awaiting kidney transplant, for ample pre-transplantation weight reduction, thus improving their accessibility to transplant. Sleeve gastrectomy can be also made use of as a post-transplantation bariatric treatment in kidney receivers, because by preserving the intestinal continuity the uptake of immunosuppressants is not disrupted. Obese made up cirrhotic patients can likewise endure LSG well. Laparoscopic SG can be securely carried out in cirrhotic patients, with low threat for postoperative problems, enhancing their metabolic disorder and reducing hepatic steatosis [24].

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is considered a contraindication for bariatric surgical procedure. However, in a research from Steed et al greater than 18% of IBD populace found to be overweight [24]. Moreover, overexpressed obesity-related cytokines play a substantial duty in the advancement of IBD [108]. Laparoscopic SG discovered to be risk-free and efficient for the management of obese patients with IBD [78,109,110]. Relating to the age of the patients LSG there are lots of researches that have actually released positive outcomes for pediatric, adolescent and geriatric patients that undertook LSG. Alqahtani et al reported their experience with LSG in youngsters and teens (5-21 years of age) with a follow-up of 24 months with really encouraging outcomes [25]. They reported no severe postoperative complications, resolution of co-morbidities and appropriate %EWL. Nevertheless, it is difficult right now to estimate the general long-lasting consequences. Consequently, these patients need to be taken care of in bariatric centers of excellence that use all available surgical choices and a stringent long-lasting follow-up [112].

Morbid obesity in elderly patients is a significant health issue. Perioperative management of clinical issues is important. Qin et al in their current multi-institutional research showed that LSG may be a more effective alternative for elderly patients [22]. Moreover, LSG can be safely carried out in senior patients, with low long-lasting reoperation and readmission threat. The perioperative danger of LSG in this patient population is mostly related to the anticipated morbidity of advanced age [23]. Other studies have likewise validated the safety and efficiency of LSG in the senior citizen populace [23]. Various other indications may consist of cases that

the little bowel is inaccessible because of adhesions from prior operations and patients in whom duplicated endoscopy of the duodenum is essential.

The only outright contraindication for performing LSG is Barrett's esophagus. The progression from abrasive reflux illness to Barrett's esophagus and gastric and esophageal cancer is well established [8]. Yet, the preoperative existence of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is only a relative contraindication, primarily as a result of the fact that reflux signs might worsen after LSG. The long-term effect of LSG in GERD is questionable. Chiu et al in their organized testimonial wrapped up that there is not enough proof to combine to a consensus concerning the impacts of LSG on GERD [8]. From the research studies they assessed, some revealed a rise in the incidence of GERD, while various other reported a decline. Himpens et al reported a biphasic pattern of GERD after LSG. Reflux signs originally existing in the first postoperative year, they gradually improve and come back after the 6th year postoperatively [5].

CONCLUSION:

Sleeve gastrectomy, also called a vertical sleeve gastrectomy, is a surgical weight-loss process. This treatment is generally performed laparoscopically, which involves placing tiny tools via numerous tiny incisions in the top abdomen. During sleeve gastrectomy, concerning 80 percent of the stomach is eliminated, leaving a tube-shaped stomach regarding the size and shape of a banana.

Restricting the dimension of the stomach limits the amount of food you have the ability to eat. Additionally, the procedure motivates hormonal changes that assist with weight reduction. The same hormone modifications also help relieve problems associated with being overweight, such as hypertension or heart disease. Sleeve gastrectomy can give lasting weight-loss. The amount of weight you shed depends upon the modification in lifestyle behaviors. It is possible to shed approximately 60 percent, or even a lot more, of the excess weight within 2 years.

Along with weight reduction, sleeve gastrectomy might boost or fix conditions connected to being overweight, consisting of: hypertension, cardiac issues, high cholesterol and inability to conceive.

It's feasible to not shed adequate weight or to gain back weight after weight-loss surgical treatment. This weight gain can occur if patient don't comply with the recommended way of living changes. If frequently treat on high-calorie foods, as an example, may have

poor weight management. To assist prevent restoring weight, patient has to make long-term healthy modifications in the diet plan and get regular physical activity and exercise.

REFERENCE:

1. Ng M et al (2014) Global, regional, and national prevalence of overweight and obesity in children and adults during 1980–2013: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013. *Lancet* 384(9945):766–781.
2. Lim SS et al (2012) A comparative risk assessment of burden of disease and injury attributable to 67 risk factors and risk factor clusters in 21 regions, 1990–2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet* 380(9859):2224–2260.
3. Li JF et al (2013) Comparison of laparoscopic Roux-en-Y gastric bypass with laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy for morbid obesity or type 2 diabetes mellitus: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Can J Surg* 56(6):E158–E164.
4. Shabbir A, Teh JL. A New Emerging procedure - Sleeve Gastrectomy. In: *Essentials and Controversies in Bariatric Surgery*. InTech; 2014.
5. Himpens J, Dobbeleir J, Peeters G. Long-term results of laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy for obesity. *Ann Surg* 2010; 252: 319-324.
6. Chambers AP, Smith EP, Begg DP, Grayson BE, Sisley S, Greer T, Sorrell J, Lemmen L, LaSance K, Woods SC, et al. Regulation of gastric emptying rate and its role in nutrient-induced GLP-1 secretion in rats after vertical sleeve gastrectomy. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab*. 2014;306:E424–E432.
7. Trung VN, Yamamoto H, Furukawa A, Yamaguchi T, Murata S, Yoshimura M, Murakami Y, Sato S, Otani H, Ugi S, et al. Enhanced Intestinal Motility during Oral Glucose Tolerance Test after Laparoscopic Sleeve Gastrectomy: Preliminary Results Using Cine Magnetic Resonance Imaging. *PLoS One*. 2013;8:e65739.
8. Chiu S, Birch DW, Shi X, Sharma AM, Karmali S. Effect of sleeve gastrectomy on gastroesophageal reflux disease: a systematic review. *Surg Obes Relat Dis* 2011; 7: 510-515.
9. Yousseif A, Emmanuel J, Karra E, Millet Q, Elkalaawy M, Jenkinson AD, Hashemi M, Adamo M, Finer N, Fiennes AG, et al. Differential effects of laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy and laparoscopic gastric bypass on appetite, circulating acyl-ghrelin, peptide YY3-36 and active GLP-1 levels in non-diabetic humans. *Obes Surg*. 2014;24:241–252.

10. Tschöp M, Smiley DL, Heiman ML. Ghrelin induces adiposity in rodents. *Nature*. 2000;407:908–913.
11. Chambers AP, Kirchner H, Wilson-Perez HE, Willency JA, Hale JE, Gaylinn BD, Thorner MO, Pfluger PT, Gutierrez JA, Tschöp MH, et al. The effects of vertical sleeve gastrectomy in rodents are ghrelin independent. *Gastroenterology*. 2013;144:50–52.e5.
12. Leibel RL, Rosenbaum M, Hirsch J. Changes in energy expenditure resulting from altered body weight. *N Engl J Med*. 1995;332:621–628.
13. Fedonidis C, Alexakis N, Koliou X, Asimaki O, Tsirimonaki E, Mangoura D. Long-term changes in the ghrelin-CB1R axis associated with the maintenance of lower body weight after sleeve gastrectomy. *Nutr Diabetes*. 2014;4:e127.
14. Ryan KK, Tremaroli V, Clemmensen C, Kovatcheva-Datchary P, Myronovych A, Karns R, Wilson-Pérez HE, Sandoval DA, Kohli R, Bäckhed F, et al. FXR is a molecular target for the effects of vertical sleeve gastrectomy. *Nature*. 2014;509:183–188.
15. Stefater MA, Pérez-Tilve D, Chambers AP, Wilson-Pérez HE, Sandoval DA, Berger J, Toure M, Tschöp M, Woods SC, Seeley RJ. Sleeve gastrectomy induces loss of weight and fat mass in obese rats, but does not affect leptin sensitivity. *Gastroenterology*. 2010;138:2426–236, 2426-236.
16. Akkary E, Duffy A, Bell R. Deciphering the sleeve: technique, indications, efficacy, and safety of sleeve gastrectomy. *Obes Surg* 2008; 18: 1323- 1329.
17. Fried M, Yumuk V, Oppert JM, Scopinaro N, Torres A, Weiner R, Yashkov Y, Fruhbeck G. Interdisciplinary European guidelines on metabolic and bariatric surgery. *Obes Surg* 2014; 24: 42-55.
18. Eid GM, Brethauer S, Mattar SG, Titchner RL, Gourash W, Schauer PR. Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy for super obese patients: forty-eight percent excess weight loss after 6 to 8 years with 93% follow-up. *Ann Surg* 2012; 256: 262-265.
19. Hidalgo JE, Roy M, Ramirez A, Szomstein S, Rosenthal RJ. Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy: a first step for rapid weight loss in morbidly obese patients requiring a second non-bariatric procedure. *Obes Surg* 2012; 22: 555-559.
20. Chaudhry UI, Kanji A, Sai-Sudhakar CB, Higgins RS, Needleman BJ. Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy in morbidly obese patients with end-stage heart failure and left ventricular assist device: medium-term results. *Surg Obes Relat Dis* 2015; 11: 88-93.
21. Tariq N, Moore LW, Sherman V. Bariatric surgery and end-stage organ failure. *Surg Clin North Am* 2013; 93: 1359-1371.
22. Qin C, Luo B, Aggarwal A, De Oliveira G, Kim JY. Advanced age as an independent predictor of perioperative risk after laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG). *Obes Surg* 2015; 25: 406-412.
23. Burchett MA, McKenna DT, Selzer DJ, Choi JH, Mattar SG. Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy is safe and effective in elderly patients: a comparative analysis. *Obes Surg* 2015; 25: 222-228.
24. Steed H, Walsh S, Reynolds N. A brief report of the epidemiology of obesity in the inflammatory bowel disease population of Tayside, Scotland. *Obes Facts* 2009; 2: 370-372.
25. Alqahtani AR, Antonisamy B, Alamri H, Elahmedi M, Zimmerman VA. Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy in 108 obese children and adolescents aged 5 to 21 years. *Ann Surg* 2012; 256: 266-273.